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INTELLECTUAL AND SPIRITUAL POTENTIAL IS A DECISIVE FACTOR IN THE SUCCESSFUL UPBRINGING OF YOUTH

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ABSTRACT

In the system of civil society, the spiritual revival of citizens occupies a key position, since spirituality improves national statehood, to the fore, putting forward the task of analyzing historical experience, reviving national and universal values in the process of building a new fair, democratic, legal, secular society with a stable market economy.

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At present, mankind has entered the third millennium, having in its arsenal vast knowledge and outstanding discoveries, which are the prerequisites for the achievement of perfection by each person. The world has developed electronics, astronautics, robotics, bioenergy, cellular communications, laser technology, a high level of use of ultraviolet and infrared rays, computer science, etc. The number of such industries, areas of science and technology that are of universal significance will grow. The decisive factor in social progress, in any social sphere, is a person. In the context of deep socio-economic and political transformations in our state, the problem of educating the younger generation and youth is of paramount importance. The processes of spiritual

revival in Uzbekistan are objectively complicated by the crisis of the ideals and aspirations of people formed in the era of socialism. In society, among some of the youth, there are dangerous tendencies of spiritual devastation, social apathy, which is typical of the era of value reorientation of society. It is impossible to recreate a new Uzbekistan with people who are unable to freely realize their potential, thinking with old stereotypes, who have not got rid of feelings of envy, fear and national inferiority, far from awareness, patriotism. The need to build a new Uzbekistan determines the education of a free-thinking, enterprising citizen - a patriot. Love for one's Motherland, pride in it, readiness for self-sacrifice for the sake of its freedom, concern for prosperity are the most important components of patriotism, which is considered one of the spiritual foundations of independence. After gaining independence, we got rid of the monopoly of the old ideology, thereby opening a wide road for the formation and development of free thought, a national ideology. Now the main task is to teach our youth to think independently, to strengthen their faith in themselves. For if thinking and consciousness are not freed from oppression and pressure, a person cannot be free. The state conducts purposeful activities in order to ensure the declared constitutional rights of citizens to spiritual improvement, taking into account the interests of all peoples and nationalities. The second part of Article 4 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan enshrined the principle "Ensuring respect for the languages, customs and traditions of nations and peoples living on the territory of Uzbekistan, as well as creating conditions for their development." The entire spiritual image of citizens reflects the attitude of the state to their traditions, customs and spiritual values. The sphere of spirituality in the Republic of Uzbekistan is recognized as a priority along with the economy, since building a legal, democratic, civil society in Uzbekistan cannot do without the development of spirituality. President I. A. Karimov highlights the problem of further spiritual renewal of society. The principles of spiritual renewal and development of Uzbekistan are based on such foundations as: - devotion to national and universal values; - Strengthening and development of the cultural heritage of the people; - free realization by a person of his capabilities; - Patriotism and humanism as the theoretical and methodological basis of national revival. Progress is provided by spiritually developed people. Mastering technical knowledge, complex technology should be combined with spiritual improvement, independent thinking. Intellectual and moral spiritual potential are two wings of an enlightened person. Today, "the decisive factor in the capabilities of every state, every nation is knowledge, education, intellectual and spiritual potential of people".

The Renaissance in Central Asia resulted in the greatest achievements in the political, economic and spiritual life of society. During this period, political and legal sciences, new literature and art, medicine, philosophy, and a new aesthetic consciousness were created.¹

As of now, the state policy of women, including women, in Uzbekistan, to protect the legitimate and social interests of women, to ensure full participation of women in the political life of the country, to ensure gender equality and reproductive health, is highly appreciated by the world community, namely, the International Labour Organization, UNICEF, the World Health Organization.²

Every social system strives for the stable functioning and formation of such a personality that

¹ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

² Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).

would correspond to its nature and essence. Social, political institutions, moral, legal and economic norms are subject to this goal. If economic growth and progress are the body of our society, then spirituality, enlightenment, the maturity of political consciousness are its spirit, mind, and soul. In this regard, higher education should educate in every citizen such a person who should be the bearer of the worldview of independence. Possess national pride, but be free from feelings of nationalism and national narrow-mindedness, think broadly, understand one's civic duty, assimilate national and spiritual values to the extent that would correspond to her professional, political and social role.

The article examines the most important issues of the formation of the rule of law and civil society in modern Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has a rich experience of political life, features of political consciousness and develops in unique and difficult conditions. Thus, it turned out that it is wrong to copy a simple copy of the political experience of the Western world.³

The paper investigates the essence of spiritual potential as well as its role in modern society.⁴

Consequently, one of the main lines in the concept of politics - improving the quality of education, the philosophy of quality in the field of education is the intellectual education of students, the formation of a new type of intelligence, a different model and way of thinking, adapted to the rapidly changing realities of the world around. The most important component of the formation of the foundations of civil society is the constant work in the field of education and spirituality, the constant improvement of the individual. This should turn into a permanent imperative, principle, basis for the development of society and represent an integral system of action, the most important place in which should be occupied by: Spirituality - Morality - Enlightenment. And what is especially important, the new generation of educated young people, free from any remnants of the past, is today becoming the decisive driving force for democratization, liberalization, renewal and confident growth of the country.

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